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Communication Strategies for Disaster Preparedness and Response in the Municipality of Daet, Camarines Norte

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I. Abstract

This study examines the communication strategies employed to enhance disaster preparedness and response in the municipality of Daet, Camarines Norte, a locality that is highly vulnerable to natural hazards such as typhoons, floods, and landslides. The research focuses on how Local Government Units (LGUs), particularly the Information Office and the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (DRRMO), disseminate information. Using the Crisis and Emergency Communication framework as a guide, the study aims to assess the effectiveness, accessibility, and challenges of communication strategies in the 17 rural barangays of Daet, where vulnerabilities are often heightened.

The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design with complementary qualitative insights, gathering 397 residents across 17 rural barangays of Daet through structured surveys and interviews. It evaluated four communication strategies, namely, electronic media, interpersonal communication, broadcast media, and print materials, along with the disaster preparedness and response phase. The findings revealed that electronic media (social media and messaging platforms) is the most widely employed communication strategy, followed by interpersonal communication, and broadcast media, while print materials remain the least utilized.

Results further indicate that broadcast and electronic media are the most effective communication channels, achieving "Highly Effective" ratings during preparedness and response, due to their reach, timeliness, and clarity. Interpersonal communication was found to be "Effective", particularly in fostering understanding and trust. Although gaps exist in feedback mechanisms and follow-up communication. In contrast, print materials consistently received the lowest effectiveness ratings, highlighting issues in design, visibility, and distribution. Overall, while the municipality demonstrates a generally functional communication system, there is a noticeable decline in communication effectiveness during the transition from preparedness to the response phase.

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The research also identified significant challenges affecting communication effectiveness. During disaster preparedness, behavioral factors such as resident complacency and disbelief in personal risk were the most prominent barriers, alongside limited resources and coordination issues. During disaster response, misinformation and rumors emerged as the most critical challenge, followed by infrastructure damage, weak communication signals, and information overload. These findings highlight that both human behavior and systematic limitations undermine the reliability and impact of disaster communication efforts.

Based on these findings, the study proposes a comprehensive policy framework entitled “Unified Disaster Communication and Coordination Ordinance of Daet,” which includes key interventions such as strengthening print-based communication, enhancing two-way feedback systems, sustaining broadcast infrastructure, improving real-time digital communication, promoting behavioral risk awareness, and establishing unified inter-agency coordination. The study concludes that while Daet has made progress in adopting multi-channel communication strategies, achieving a resilient disaster communication system requires integrated, inclusive, and institutionalized approaches that address both technological and behavioral dimensions of communication.

II. Keywords: *Disaster Communication, Disaster Preparedness, Disaster Response, Crisis and Emergency Communication, Local Government Units (LGUs)*